

Teachers' Perspective on Successful Transition planning in Secondary Level special education schools for Hearing Impaired Students

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ABSTRACT: Transition planning is crucial for students with hearing impairment before leaving school. Teachers have the key responsibility in transition planning. This study was qualitative and explanatory. The sample of study were the teachers (N = 20) from the special education schools for hearing-impaired students. A self-developed semi-structured interview protocol was administered to collect data by using the purposive sampling technique. Data was analyzed through coding and thematic analysis. Six major themes emerged from the data analysis i.e., teachers' perception, ways to ensure, active role of students, challenges for hearing-impaired students, future Challenges for Hearing impaired students, strategies for successful transition planning. Findings of study revealed that majority of the teachers perceive that practices of transition plan in special education is based on understanding the interest, guidance for students, avoidable practices, parents' participation, and opportunities of vocational trainings. The study recommends that suitable guidance and counselling services should be provided in the schools to students with hearing impairment about effective transition from school.

Keywords: Transition plan, Hearing impaired students, Special education, Trends, Schools.

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1. Introduction

Transition refers to a change from one phase to another. For this purpose, post-high school objectives that are determined and created under students' needs, interests, capabilities, and abilities that are referred to as transition plans. A comprehensive and well directed transition plan becomes a beacon for students especially with hearing impairment after completion of their secondary education in special education schools. Effective

transition plan reflects the efforts of the teachers that helps the students to achieve their life goals.

Planning for transitions has to take into account the needs of the community as well as the individual. For the outcome to be effective, these two levels must intersect, yet for each to be implemented well, distinct planning and cognitive processes are needed. In general, there are numerous approaches to assist students in leading and going through a positive transition, guaranteeing behavioral and academic engagement, and experiencing a feeling of community inside their school (Andrew et al., 2024). The process of transition is outcome-driven and personally motivated by each student's aspiration for an adult life (Wehman et al., 2018).

Children with hearing loss may experience difficulties with speech, language, development, schooling, and cognitive functions if they do not receive hearing therapy (Lieu et al., 2020). Hearing impairment can have a significant impact on the education of students with hearing impairment. Completing a degree involves many barriers for students with hearing impairments (Ain, 2021). Hearing-impaired students may have difficulty communicating with others, which can lead to social isolation and feelings of frustration or inadequacy. However, with the right support and accommodations, students with hearing impairment can overcome these challenges and achieve success through classroom learning. In addition to other supports like personal assistance, sign language interpreters, and barrier removal, assistive technology is essential to advancing the inclusion of people with disabilities (Soetan et al., 2020).

Transition planning is crucial for hearing-impaired students because it helps them prepare for the challenges of post-secondary education or employment. This is the point at which life outside school starts and formal education finishes (Patton & Kim, 2016). These students may require additional support and accommodations to succeed in these environments, and transition planning can help ensure they have the necessary resources. By identifying their strengths, interests, and goals, hearing-impaired students can create a plan that meets their unique needs and sets them up for success. The methods usually involve using a different sense (Kushawaha & Ahuja, 2024). Additionally, transition planning can help these students build the skills they need to communicate effectively, advocate for themselves, and navigate new environments. Without transition planning, hearing-impaired students may struggle to succeed in post-secondary education or employment, which can limit their opportunities and impact their quality of life. The important period in the lives of the children and their families is the school transition (Bagnall et al., 2022). Overall, transition planning is a vital component of ensuring that hearing-impaired students have the support they need to achieve their full potential. Achieving the best possible post-school outcome for these students depends in large part on the transition education, planning, and practices they receive while in secondary school (Alsalamah & Poppen, 2022). Because, the transition planning process is always based on the post-school goals.

Teachers play a critical role in the transition planning process for hearing-impaired students. So, it is important to improve the professional skills of teachers (Fayzullaevna et al., 2020). Teachers can help them identify their strengths, interests, and goals, and develop a plan to achieve them. For hearing-impaired students, this process may require

additional support and accommodations to ensure they have the tools they need to succeed. Overall, the role of teachers in transition planning is to help hearing-impaired students prepare for a successful future and achieve their full potential.

Rationale of Research

The reason for doing this research is to promote successful transition planning of hearing-impaired students from school to post-secondary education or employment. Special education has its apex responsibility to work for the best possible accommodation of the students with hearing impairment soon after their schooling either for education or the workplace. Therefore, teachers' strategies may help students understand things better (Karuppannan et al., 2021).

Statement of Problem

Promoting transition planning for hearing-impaired students in special schools at the secondary level is important. Its impact is positive on the students with hearing impairment after secondary education. Despite significant advancements in educational accommodations and support services for hearing-impaired students, there exists a critical issue surrounding the effectiveness of transition planning at the secondary level. Many hearing-impaired students face challenges when transitioning from secondary school to post-secondary education, employment, or independent living. This problem is worsened by a lack of comprehensive research that addresses the specific barriers, strategies, and best practices required to ensure successful transitions for these students. Consequently, there is an urgent need for an in-depth investigation into the factors influencing the success of transition planning for hearing-impaired students at the secondary level, with a focus on identifying practical solutions that can bridge the existing gap in their educational journey and foster greater independence and integration into society."

Objectives of Study

The objectives of the research were to:

1. Find out the existing status of transition planning for the students with hearing impaired in special education schools by teachers demographic age, gender, and experience.
2. Explore the active role of students about transition planning through their teachers of hearing impairment field.
3. Identify the challenges faced by students with hearing impairment in transition planning.
4. Inquire the future challenges faced by students with hearing impaired by their teachers' perspective.
5. Suggest suitable strategies for the successful transition planning of students with hearing-impairment at school level.

Questions of the Study

The questions of the research were:

1. What is the existing status of transition planning for the students with hearing impaired in special education schools by teachers demographic age, gender, and experience?
2. What is the active role of students about transition planning through their teachers of hearing impairment field?
3. What are the challenges faced by students with hearing impairment in transition planning?
4. What are the future challenges faced by students with hearing impaired by their teachers' perspective.
5. What are the ways for the successful transition planning of students with hearing impairment at school level?

Significance of the Research

Transition planning is an essential aspect of education for students with hearing impairments at the secondary level. It involves preparing students for the transition from secondary school to post-secondary education, employment, and independent living. This process aims to equip students with the necessary skills, knowledge, and support to achieve successful outcomes in their adult lives.

Transition planning for students with hearing impairments is of utmost importance for several reasons. Firstly, it ensures that these students have equal opportunities for success and independence beyond their secondary education. By identifying their unique needs and strengths, transition planning can help tailor educational programs and support services to meet those needs effectively.

One significant benefit of conducting this research is the potential to improve educational outcomes for the students with hearing impaired students. By identifying best practices, strategies, and interventions that support successful transitions, educators, administrators, and policymakers can make informed decisions and implement effective programs.

Moreover, this research can bring awareness to the challenges faced by students with hearing impairments during their transition from secondary school to adulthood. It can highlight the importance of early intervention, individualized education plans (IEPs), and collaboration between educators, families, and related service providers. Therefore, this research can contribute to the development of inclusive policies and practices that promote the success of students with hearing impairment.

Teachers and educators will benefit from a deeper understanding of effective instructional strategies and accommodations that can be implemented in the transition planning of students with hearing impairment. They can gain insights into creating supportive learning environments that foster the development of essential skills for transition, such as communication, self-advocacy, and problem-solving. Additionally, families of students with hearing impairments will benefit from the research by gaining knowledge and resources to support their child's transition process. Understanding the available options and support systems can empower families to actively participate in the planning and decision-making processes, ensuring that their child's individual needs are met effectively.

Furthermore, policymakers and administrators can utilize the findings of this research to develop the comprehensive policies and guidelines that address the specific needs of students with hearing impairments during the transition period.

Limitations of the Research

There were following limitation of the study:

1. The study was limited to the province of the Punjab only as the researchers were unable to cover other provinces due to time and financial constraints.

Delimitations of the study

Following were the delimitations of the study

1. The researchers used a self-developed instrument for the data collection process due to the unavailability of the standardized instrument.
2. Only the teachers from special education schools for hearing impairment students were taken as a sample of this study.

2. Literature Review

According to (Maryanti et al., 2021), Hearing Impairment is one of the permanent unique needs, which causes them to struggle with communicating. It does, in fact, have an impact on how well students comprehend the lessons and materials they are taught. When instructing students with HI, the majority of teachers encounter challenges (Hidayat, 2021). In reality, educators in schools require a thorough understanding of how to instruct students with hearing impairment. Furthermore, a large number of young people with disabilities are not receiving the transition-related education and services they need in order to succeed beyond school (Trainor et al., 2020).

Educational program must include transition planning as required by the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act. Teachers need to be well-versed in both the material and pedagogical aspects of the transition planning process in order to carry out this responsibility. According to (Deardorff et al., 2021).

The shift from secondary school to post-school life, education, and employment can be difficult for young people who are deaf or hard of hearing (Todorov et al., 2021). For these children to obtain the best post-school results, transition education, planning, and practices during their secondary education are crucial (Todorov et al., 2021). The term "transition" describes the shift from one phase to another. The goal of high school transition planning is to facilitate a smooth transition to adulthood (Wehman et al., 2018). The process of transitioning served as a methodical advancement of developing abilities and encounters from the beginning of a student's academic journey until graduation. Transition planning centers on a crucial but intricate stage in the life of a young person, during which time their supports system, expectations, and the social environment as a whole will undergo changes (Wehman et al., 2018). Every student experiences anxiety during the transition to high school, but students with disabilities may experience it more than others due to their higher likelihood of difficulties in the areas of academics, Socio-emotion, self-determination,

and other areas (Han et al., 2021). With the support of this all-encompassing strategy, which is based on best practices and research, instructors may effectively mentor children through the transition to secondary school and beyond. For those without impairments, the move from high school to college can be difficult. During this shift, schools frequently ignore and overburden kids with impairments, which causes an achievement gap for them (Santos et al., 2022).

3. Methodology of The Research

Research Design

This research was qualitative in approach and exploratory in nature.

Population of the Research

The population of the research was the teachers of hearing-impaired students from special education schools in the province of Punjab.

Sample of the Research

The sample of the research was the teachers of hearing-impaired field (N=20) teaching at special education schools for hearing-impaired children in the province of Punjab. The sample was taken from various cities of Punjab including Lahore (N=07), Khanewal (N=03), Sargodha (N=2), Sahiwal (N=1), Toba Tek Singh (N=1), Talagang (N=1), Bahawalnagar (N=1), Bahawalpur (N=1), Rawalpindi (N=1), Rahim yar khan (N=1) and Kasur (N=1).

Table 1: Samples' Demographics

Sample	Demographics Detail
Gender	Male 13, Female 07
Age	25-30 (05), 30-35 (04), 35-40(06), above 40 (05)
Experience	Below 5 years (5), above 5 years (15)
Qualification	BS/M. A/M.Ed. (10), MS/M.Phil. (9), PHD (01)
Designation	JSET (04), SSET (13), others (03)

Instrument for Data Collection

On the basis of the literature review and the objectives of the study, A semi-structured interview was developed as a research instrument to collect data from teachers of the hearing impairment field. The instrument was consisted of 2 parts: Section one of the instrument was Demographic information of the participants including Name, Gender, Age, Education, District, and School Name. Section two consisted of 9 open-ended questions and many probing questions to generate maximum information regarding transition planning of students with hearing impairment.

Validity & Reliability of the Instrument

A panel of expert (N=02) was approached to ensure the validity of the content of the instrument. Each item of the instrument was consulted with field experts and each item's application was reviewed, updated, and revised with the expert's opinion. Initially, 9 questions related to the context of questions of the study were validated by teachers.

Moreover, the reliability of the instrument was examined through an extensive review of the literature.

Data Collection Procedure

For data collection all ethical considerations were determined, consent of respondents to conduct the interview. The researcher read and interpreted the instrument while interviewing the participants in their native language. Each interview took 15 to 20 minutes. The responses of the participants were recorded and noted accordingly. Later on, responses of the participants were transcribed and reported by the researchers.

Data Analysis

After the collection of the data, the interview responses of the participants were transcribed and open coding was applied to generate categories. The categories were further elaborated with sub-themes. Then, the major themes were drawn to reach towards findings of the research. The themes were also supported by the relevant literature. At the end of the analysis, a summary of the research, findings, and conclusion were drawn and recommendations were made.

Ethical Consideration of the Research

Ethical considerations are very crucial in research as it is important to prioritize the well-being and rights of participants. This means obtaining informed consent, ensuring confidentiality and privacy, and minimizing any potential harm. Researchers should also strive for transparency, honesty, and fairness throughout the entire research process.

4. Qualitative Data Analysis

Coding & Thematic Analysis

Research Question 1: What is the existing status of transition planning for the students with hearing impairment in special education schools?

Theme 1: Teacher's Perception

This theme depicts the responses of participants about the perception of the teachers regarding existing status of transition planning in special education schools for hearing impairment students. The theme has been emerged from the categories i.e, understanding the interest, guidance for students, avoidable practices, parents' participation, and opportunities of vocational trainings. The outcomes for the child is based on the role of the parents in the education of their children (Ahmed et al., 2024).

Category 1: Understanding the Interest

This category shows that half of the participants responded that understanding students' interests with Hearing impairment is important for teachers. These participants also narrated that transition planning of hearing-impaired students is based on the child's interest learn vocational skill or future education. However, 1 of the participants reported that

"Transition Plan is made accordingly because these children are better at drawing and art so, they are taken forward according to their interests."

Category 2: Guidance for Students

This category depicts that majority of participants responded that the guidance for students with hearing impairment about transition planning should be provided at school the participants of the study revealed that students with hearing impairment should be guided properly by their teachers at school. Additionally, 1 of the participants expressed that

"Children should be guided accordingly for their future activities. They should be well aware of all their transition endeavors."

Category 3: Avoidable Practices

This category contains the responses of participants about the non-implementation of the transition plan in schools for hearing-impaired students. The participants of the study revealed that there is avoidance in making the transition plan in the schools. One of the participants stated that "The transition plan is not followed. It is only limited to documents. School do not apply it."

Category 4: Parents Participation

This category states that majority of participants narrated the participation of the guardian for hearing-impaired students in special education schools. The participants of the study narrated that in transition planning guardian participation is very important for hearing-impaired students. One of the participants explained that

"The involvement of parents is very important because it is the parents who support their children in every phases of the life."

Category 5: Opportunities of Vocational Trainings

This category shows the response of half of the participants about vocational training for hearing-impaired students in special education schools. The participants of the study expressed that vocational training is used for transition skills in special education schools for hearing-impaired students. 1 of the participants explained that

"Vocational training is used for transition skills and after 8, admissions are given in the computer, beautician, etc. in areas like Lahore."

Theme 2: Ways to Ensure

This theme expresses ways of ensuring the transition planning of hearing-impaired children in special education schools by their teachers. The theme contains the categories that are follow-up of ex-students, interest based approach, assessing progress, and professional support. The theme explains the comprehensive ways of ensuring transition planning for hearing-impaired students. In secondary schools, transition planning and service determination for children with disabilities fall under the responsibility of special education teachers (Plotner et al., 2016).

Category 1: Follow-up of Ex-students

This category depicts that very few participants stated that they keep information of only those students who passed out their matriculation from their school. These participant of the study expressed that they know what the students are doing after matriculation. Additionally, one of the participants narrated that

“If the child is interested in computers, then he will be taught computer programs, and we try to judge from his documentation and daily routine in which direction the child is inclined.”

Category 2: Interest Based Approach

This category depicts that majority of the participants responded that they guide the students according to their interests. The participants narrated that some students are interested in studying and ask them for opportunities. It was also revealed by some of the participants that student's performance can also been seen their notebooks. Additionally, one of the participants expressed that

“If the student is interested in computers, then he will be taught computer programs, and we try to judge from his documentation and daily routine in which direction the student is inclined.”

Category 3: Assessing Progress

This category represents that half of the participants responded that assessment of the students help the teachers to get to know about the student's interest in the employment or the further studies. The participants of the study narrated that formative and summative assessments are conducted for the sake of right assessment for right students. 1 of the participants explained that

“After assessment, it will be known whether the student is ready for employment or for higher education.”

Category 4: Professionals' Support

This category reflects the responses of the participants about the professional's support in the environment of special education schools for hearing impaired students. The participants of the study revealed that various teams in special education work always for the betterment of the students with hearing impairment. If the teams of the professional

discuss time to time the matters of students with hearing impairment. One of the participants described that

“The teachers will give their input regarding the child. The teachers will tell what deficiency they have seen in the students, and what they do all the time.”

Theme 3: Foundation of Students' Active Role

This theme reflects the active role of the students with hearing in their education and transition planning. The theme has been emerged from the categories of skill based education, empowering the students, individualized education, and reinforcement. Students who are deaf or hard of hearing have particular needs when the matter is of their education (Bowen & Probst, 2023).

Category 1: Skill Based Education

This category states that majority of participants narrated that skill based training for the hearing-impaired students in the special education school is complied during their schooling education. The participants of the study endorsed on skill based education for hearing-impaired students. 1 of the participant stated that

“If you tell them that there are vocational colleges, go and visit them and resources are available there.”

Category 2: Empowering the Students

This category shows the responses of the participants that empowering the students with hearing impairment is the main focus of the teachers in special education schools. However, the participant also expressed that students with hearing impairment feel difficulty due to severe communication barriers in building their confidence. One of the participants described that

“Confidence will develop in children and children's minds will be clear, they will learn and read things confidentially.”

Category 3: Individualized Education

This category depicts that half of the participants responded about the individual education in the school of special education for hearing-impaired students. The participants of the study revealed that students with hearing impairment could be personalized learning paths in individual education for HI students in special education schools. 1 of the participants narrated that

“The interests of all children will be different from each other, some children will be interested in computers, and some children interested in art and drawing, then the teacher will place them according to their interest.”

Category 4: Reinforcement

This category shows the responses of only few participants about the reinforcement of hearing-impaired students in special education schools. The participants of the study state that reinforcement is important in special education schools for hearing-impaired students. 1 of the participants that

“If we see a child who is not doing well in his studies, we will explain to him that he should focus more on his studies or else take an interest in some other work or he should go towards earning.”

Research Question 2: What are the challenges faced by students with hearing impairment in transition planning?

Theme 4: Challenges In Transition Planning

This theme displays the challenges in transition planning for students with hearing impairment. The theme has been emerged from the categories of communication barriers, unsupportive parents', employment problems, and educational limitations. The classroom can pose challenges for students who have hearing loss, potentially resulting in their social isolation (Krishnan et al., 2020).

Category 1: Communication Barriers

This category shows the response of majority of participants about barriers in communication and they talk about the weakness of the writing skills of hearing-impaired students. The participants of the study say that due to the communication gap, students can't easily communicate with others. 1 of the participants explained that

“Communication barrier because not everyone knows sign language and even parents don't know sign language, so there is a huge communication gap due to which children are not able to communicate well in the society.”

Category 2: Unsupportive Parents'

This category depicts the response of only few of the participants about parents' support for transition plan for the hearing-impaired children. The participants of the study revealed that parents have less understanding about transition plan and they do not support their children especially with hearing impairment for effective transitioning. These participants further added that parents do not prepare their children for successful transition. One of the participants explained that

“The challenge for them may be that parents do not allow them to pursue their interests and want to involve them in their home business.”

Category 3: Employment Problems

This category contains the responses of majority of the participants about employment challenges for hearing-impaired students. The participants further described that they cannot earn well and face challenges. One of the participants explain that

“There are so many challenges for a normal person in Pakistan, then this is a special child, they will have to face challenges in employment, they will not be able to generate good income and they will have to face too many challenges in future”

Category 4: Educational Limitations

This category displays the responses of the participants about the educational limitations that are experienced by students with hearing impairment. These participants also stated that educational limitations are due to fewer opportunities in various field of educational domains. This becomes great challenge for students with hearing impairment in the implementation of transition planning. One of the participants narrated that

“If we talk about the various options for students with hearing impairment including businesses, shop keeping or etc then the students require specific guidelines which could meet their special needs but in our country, there is no such opportunity for them due to educational limitations.”

Research Question 3: What are the future challenges faced by students with hearing impairment by their teachers' perspective?

Theme 5: Future Challenges for Students with Hearing Impairment

This theme depicts the future challenges for hearing-impaired students. The theme contains categories which are unemployment, non-acceptance by society, poor socioeconomic status, improper guidelines, and limited educational resources. Students who are deaf or hard of hearing face multiple barriers during their education. The already challenging transition from high school to college is made worse by aspects of deaf language, culture, learning, and communication styles, as well as a lack of support resources (Adkins, 2020).

Category 1: Unemployment

This category contains the responses of majority of participants about the unemployment in future for students with hearing impairment as a result of ineffective transition planning. These participants narrated that students with hearing impairment face unemployment challenge in their future because of their dependability on others. One of the participants explained that

“If the transition planning for the students is not in-line properly then he will not get a suitable job. This will decrease their motivation to do job.”

Category 2: Non Acceptance by Society

This category depicts the responses of half of the participants about society do not accept hearing-impaired children. The participants further say that they also have social issues. One of the participants described that

“The child becomes a problem for the family and also for himself and it becomes very difficult to adjust in the society.”

Category 3: Poor Socioeconomic Status

This category depicts the responses of less than half of the participants about poor socioeconomic status as a future challenge for students with hearing impairment. These participants explained that parents send their children with hearing impairment for any labour work and for this reason, students with hearing impairment leave their studies. One of the participants said that

“If there is no planning, if the parents are not properly guided, then they do not give education to the child after matriculation, they directly send him to a shop or make him sit at home.”

Category 4: Improper Guidelines

This category depicts the responses of majority of the participants about the decision making for hearing impaired students by their teachers or the parents. These participants further endorsed that improper decision making of the teachers or even the parents put the students with hearing impairment on very difficult and ineffective track. One of the participants explained that

“If children will not be properly prepared and will not be able to understand things, their main thing is decision-making. If the transition planning is not done properly, they will have to face many challenges.”

Category 5: Limited Educational Resources

This category shows the responses of the majority of the participants about the challenges in education for students with hearing impairment that remain in the future at the time of the transition. These participants expressed that students with hearing impairment experience numerous challenges in their education that affect their future life at the time of transition from school to higher education. One of the participants explained that

“They have to face challenges because children can't even write their names and our system is not so supported that the child could work easily. Syllabus is so much that children avoid study, the biggest challenge for them is study due to communication problem.”

Research Question 4: What are the ways for the successful transition planning of students with hearing impairment at school level?

Theme 6: Strategies for Successful Transition Planning

This theme reflects the responses of the participants about strategies for successful transition planning. This theme contains categories that are awareness for transition planning, vocational training for hearing-impaired students, guidance for parents, and effective programming. The theme explains a comprehensive successful transition planning. Special education teachers equip these individuals with the necessary skills and knowledge to smoothly transition into the workforce by implementing effective instructional techniques (Conag et al., 2023).

Category 1: Awareness for Transition Planning

This category shows that the majority of the participants responded that should also have awareness about transition planning in the school of special education for hearing-impaired students. In this category, these participants narrated that awareness should be for hearing-impaired students in special education schools. 1 of the participants said that

"Awareness is an integral part."

Category 2: Vocational Training for Hearing Impaired Students

This category states that majority of the participants said that about vocational training for hearing-impaired students in special education schools. The participants of the study stated that vocational training should be provided in special education schools for hearing-impaired students. One of the participants responded that

"Children should be given as much vocational training as possible and their teachers should be given sign language training."

Category 3: Guidance for Parents

This category contains the responses of participants about the guidance to the parents in special education schools for hearing-impaired students. In this category majority participants responded that the teacher guides the parents to play their role with their hearing-impaired children. 1 of the participants expressed that

"Properly guide the parents the way we guide the children."

Category 4: Effective Programming

This category depicts that half of the participants responded about the effectiveness of individualized education programs, individualized transition plans, and the entrepreneurship programs for students with hearing impairment. The study participant revealed that there should be firm planning for students with hearing impairment, especially in their transition planning, and individualized education programs. One of the participants expressed that

"Students with hearing impairment have mostly financial problems in their families. They should be taught the education of entrepreneurship."

One more participant said that

"There is no such practice of making I.E. P's or transition planning in special education schools but it should be."

5. Findings

By keeping in view the qualitative data analysis of this study, followings are the appropriate findings:

Teacher's Perception

This study found that teachers perceive about the existing status of transition planning in special education schools for hearing-impaired students is complied with understanding the interest, guidance for students, avoidable practices, parents' participation, and opportunities of vocational trainings.

Ways to Ensure

This study found that the ways to ensure transition planning of hearing-impaired students in special education schools are follow-up of ex-students, interest based approach, assessing progress, and professional support.

Active role of students with hearing-impairment

This study found active role of students with hearing impairment in transition planning is skill based education, empowering the students, individualized education, and reinforcement.

Challenges in Transition Planning

This study found the challenges of students with hearing impairment in transition planning are communication barriers, unsupportive parents, employment problems, and educational limitations.

Future Challenges for Students with Hearing Impairment

This study found the future challenges for the students with hearing impairment in the transition planning can be unemployment, non-acceptance by society, poor socioeconomic status, improper guidelines, and limited educational resources.

Strategies for successful transition planning

This study found that suitable strategies for successful transition planning are awareness for transition planning, vocational training for hearing-impaired students, guidance for parents, and effective programming.

6. Discussion

Transition planning is most important in the life of children with disabilities. Transition planning for hearing-impaired students is crucial to help them smoothly move from school to the next phase of their lives. This planning is like making a roadmap for the future. It involves thinking about what comes after high school, like college, work, or vocational training. Teachers and counselors work closely with students, their families, and support services to identify goals and strengths. They help students learn important skills, like communication and self-advocacy, to prepare them for success in their next life.

Teachers play a critical role in the transition planning process for hearing-impaired students. So, it is important to improve the professional skills of teachers (Fayzullaevna et al., 2020). The perceptions of teachers about transition plans for students with hearing

impairment are different from each other. Some teachers' opinions are about understanding the interests of the students with hearing impairment. However, few teachers have different perceptions about the transition planning of students with hearing impairment. They thought that proper guidance would be provided to the students with hearing impairment. There are numbers of teachers of hearing-impaired students in the special education schools who empower the students for success and they also explore the interest of the students with hearing impairment. Teachers understand the value of using multisensory teaching methods, visual aids, sign language, and other tools in addition to customizing the curriculum to fit the requirements of these students. However, there was less agreement found in using of technology and for that more research is necessary (Perveen et al., 2024). The participation of students with hearing impairment in their transition plays a crucial role. According to Visser et al., (2023), interventions aimed at helping students make the transition to secondary education may benefit from placing a strong focus on developing autonomy-related abilities. The active involvement of students in the planning process empowers them to express their unique needs, preferences, and aspirations. Students can work with teachers, support staff, and parents to create a transition plan that fits their objectives. This can improve student involvement (Halverson & Graham, 2019).

Students with hearing impairment experience a lot of challenges in their transition planning in special education schools for hearing impairment. They face unemployment challenges. Students with hearing impairment also face educational challenges due to their communication barriers. Communication is hampered by deafness. It results in a barrier or communication gap between the hearing community and the deaf individual (Sabato et al., 2023). These children also have to face the fact that society does not accept them. That could be one of the issues preventing them from fully and actively engaging in society (Krishnan et al., 2020)

Teachers use different strategies for the transition planning of students with hearing impairment in special education schools. Teachers gave them awareness about the transition plan for hearing-impaired students. Only when teachers are up to date on the latest information and new trends then successful transition planning can be accomplished (Manzoor et al., 2023).

Teacher guides to the parents of students with hearing impairment. Teachers provide vocational training to students with hearing impairment in special education schools. It is important to consider carefully how well these strategies work to overcome those barriers (Mansutti et al., 2022).

7. Conclusion

The results of the study are concluded here with the perception of teachers who have a better understanding of transition planning for hearing-impaired students. The significance of the shift for students with disabilities from educational programs in public schools to suitable postsecondary experiences, as well as the support services required to make the move. Teachers of hearing-impaired students observe the interests of the students and then make them work according to their interests. Different resources are available for the students with hearing impaired students. Transition planning can be

adopted through proper resources. These plans help students set goals and develop essential skills needed for success in the adult world. By working closely with teachers, counselors, and support services, students can build their confidence and independence. Most students play an active role in their transition planning. Instruction on how to actively participate in evaluation, planning, and the achievement of annual transition goals must be incorporated into transition education methods to increase student participation. Mostly students with hearing impairment face challenges during transition planning and after transition planning due to ineffective transition planning. Teachers of students with hearing impairment are required to develop different strategies for transition planning for the students with hearing impairment.

8. Recommendations

The recommendations of the study have been mentioned below:

1. Suitable guidance and counselling services should be provided in the schools to students with hearing impairment about effective transition from school.
2. Teachers of the students with hearing impairment should be provided be appropriate resources in the school to prepare their students with hearing impairment for an efficacious transition from school to their next life.
3. Special education department Punjab should provide policy guidelines in the special education schools for hearing impaired students' teachers about transition planning of students with hearing impairment.
4. Special education schools for hearing impaired students should ensure the parents' participation in the education and transition of hearing-impaired students for the sake of making them independent.
5. Stakeholders of the community should be given awareness to accommodate the students with hearing impairment regarding transition from school to work-place.
6. Future researchers should conduct a study with quantitative or mixed method approaches to explore the same phenomenon with different perspective.

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